

LEON GOLUB AND HIS ENDLESS CANVAS

ARSALAN TIGHNAVARD

ART THEORY

2024

LEON GOLUB AND HIS ENDLESS CANVAS

The atmosphere and currents of art in 20th century is highly wide that it is somewhat complex to specify dates to each of them. There were some theories of art and philosophy and theoretician that influenced each movement every decade. In the meanwhile, some disappeared and others could survive for more decades. Some of them in their heyday influenced their ongoing movement and others were opposed to their next currents. In a sense, it should be said that every new era brings new synthesis that was against its previous thesis in art. After every synthesis, it is about to show up new anti-synthesis or the combination their last two movements and theories. In addition, sometimes a repetitive manner after long time can regenerate its feature in history again. One of the example of this situation occurred in art in 70s. in other words, from 1972 onwards, there were currents in figurative art. And in this notion, the insight to the environment was becoming more important. The regeneration of figurative art happened in a time when some catastrophes happened in the Asia, united Stated and some other areas. Not only these events in history but some psychological impact were significant to this new feature in art, especially painting in that time.

¹ SMART MUSEUM OF ART, THE UNIVERSITY OF CHICAGO, THE ROSTER: LEON GOLUB, <https://smartmuseum.uchicago.edu/blog/the-roster-leon-golub/>

in this essay I have chosen Leon Golub who among others were immensely influential and his work was widely provocative. He with others Eric Fischl and Jean-Michel Basquiat, Philip Guston, Alice Neel and Julian Schnabel were effective to reborn figurative paintings. Their consistency and insistence on figuration, being neglected from art market made their art more effective. And too they were impressive to lead and return to figurative art to particular subjects like politic, social in 1970s and 80s. this feature and act was paralleled notably with number of artists and writers and their radical reaction towards wars, especially in United States. They influenced on their next currents of art which are called post-post-modern art and post conceptual art and Neo-geo in 1990. In Golub's case, there are numbers of influences and interests of artist in his work in each decade and to ease following the essay I decide to go through his work chronologically to understand why he was shifting to specific feature and approach to attain what he was supposed to show in his works to the others and viewers.

The transition from abstract and abstract expressionism to figuration is akin to periods in the past even in ancient times. My intention of giving this rare and far example is meant to see two immense divergent approaches in art coming afterwards one another, This kind of contradiction between two consecutives approaches in art can have underlying aspects rooted in social, cultural values, political, economical issues in specific areas. This is what occur in the taste of art in 2nd century with naturalistic and realistic approaches and the transition to abstract notion in art with the rise of Christianity. In this notion, there are always this kind of shift from 2 different approaches. This type of change in art is inevitable with one artist with its forerunner and in

other cases according to Ernst Gombrich². Furthermore, the logical aspects of this cycle where highest point of abstraction ends up with the opposite will and give rise to figuration. For instance, Art in prehistoric era was with the purpose of representing religious and communal beliefs in which one does not need necessarily to have a realistic approach. It is mentioned that the goal of these works were not realism. However, in 4th BC, Greco-Roman began to move to realistic expression such as Stoicism and concentrated on human and figurative language³. It was the point where the archaic art and classical logic is more touchable in terms of their intended use. This or other kind of controversial changes and substitutions have been common in history of art and are based on changes in society, philosophy and other decisive aspects.

Biography

American artist, Leon Golub was born in 1922 in Chicago, Illinois, receiving BA at the university of Chicago in the history of classical art and in painting at the school of the art Institute of Chicago. He dealt with social realism and figurative expressionism in his artistic practice. Since the mainstream of art put more attention to Abstract Expressionism, he was neglected as a painter creating good art even if he was prolific in paintings. Anyhow, after living some years in Europe he came back again with his wife to United States to proceed his art hopping to have space and be seen more by American artsy with the aid of other happenings from writers and artists who were aligned with his approach.

² The Story of Art, preface, 13, 1950

³ “The Return of Figurative Painting?”, Sarah Kim, t’art, 2022

Initial steps & influences

He was a painter, studied in America, in academic situations, having modern approach. His aspect was then changed. He aspect was changed with his insight into American lifestyle and American imperial culture. In a sense, he was suffering from the style and his artwork becoming radical. But he couldn't be able to succeed in that time.

he is a content oriented artist. As he mentioned: "I focus on what the images are about". He calls himself as a history painter. Figures are the integral part of paintings to him and having stable approach as an artist. Yet, he was neglected by art auction and art world for many years due to his radical taste in depicting alternative scenes.

his earliest style is expressionism in painting figures and emphasis on texture. Once he pointed out that in his earlier work he was highly influenced by the sort of rough texture that Jean Dubuffet applied in his paintings.⁴ In addition, in his entire career he was influenced with a broad names of artist based on techniques, contents and methods. However, he did not stick with specific approach since his prospect and mindset behind works of art was linked to content rather than aesthetic styles. It should be said that both factors were integral but he did apply them for the certain intention. This is extremely prominent and delicate in artists' career since it may drive artists to a fixed style in content to create repetitive works rather than enhancing or even coming up with new content.

the influential artists and painters in his work is innumerable as he mentioned in various interviews. Those who were mentioned by Golub and others who indirectly have slight impact in

⁴ Leon Golub, interviewed by Bruce Hooton, 1965

his work. In each example, I try to mention those influences on Golub's paintings. he consciously moved against the opposite mainstream of art from 40s until the end of his life. He kept his style even for years when he was rejected and ignored by art world. Ultimately, he became a genre in the market of art in America. He may suddenly confronted with question like representation or non-objectivism, or how a man can be represented in art. Therefore, his tendencies to figurative depiction in spite of longing to texture and other aesthetic feature, his consciousness towards being creative were two undeniable clues among other things to strengthened his genre in painting.

Moving to Europe

Leon Golub: Bite Your Tongue, Serpentine Gallery, 2015

As it is mentioned, he was not successful in America, since the mainstream of art was following

those who worked and had minimalistic and expressionism approaches. His aspect was changed with his approach with American lifestyle and culture. Suddenly, we can see the opposition of his mind with American lifestyle. In a sense, he was suffering from the style and his artwork becoming radical. But he couldn't be able to succeed in that time.

Then, he moved to Europe, and worked many years. It is one of the reasons why he became well-known later. Not because of the area and zone but because of his political and social observation.

In Europe, he worked with some galleries. because in America, art world found hostile to figurative painters. In Italy and France, he looked at Etruscan and Roman art.

he was interested in process of technical style and figurative image.

spending 9 months in Italy and living in Paris from 1959 to 1964 supported by Herbert

Greenwald. In 1956, he moved to Florence, Herculaneum and Pompeii, and working and

studying Hellenistic and archaeology in Rome afterwards. He used classical sources. This was the time that had a decisive role in the language and expression in his late collections, since he

visited ancient sites and great Italian museums.⁵ One of the tangible example of this kind impact

can be traced from one of his work called "Gigantomachy II" in which he was surprisingly

influenced by Roman and Greek Art.⁶ It can be said that this work was the consequence of his

time discovering history and being influenced by Roman, and Greek arts and cultures. As it is

shown in the painting, the figures are somewhat vulnerable and at the same time heroic. In a

sense, the violation in the act of figures and the contradiction of definition of being a person as a

hero is being question by him. Under the circumstances, this could be a suggestion to what

⁵ According to Jon Bird, he visited Naples Museum that reinforced his earlier art-historical and aesthetic interests.

⁶ "Influence of the great "Altar of Zeus at Pergamon"". Bird, Leon Golub, Echoes of the Real, 25

Declan McGonagle ⁷ questioned regarding this sort of combination “why classical figure should be represented as violence”.⁸ Leon Golub, in an interview with Bruce Hooton, claimed that I’m very much influenced by things like Pergamon, late Roman sculpture, portrait busts, and so on.⁹ Taking one figure out of the rest, retaining or changing the position of figure. The background is timeless and dislocation. Taking the advantage of abstract expressionism in this period was prior to his later red flatted color in the “Interrogation” series. Here, had has Abstract Expressionism and classical figurative expression at the same time. Since the work is painted in huge size, a small detail of this work may confuse every visitor to recognize artist distinct intention. In addition, nudity of men who are fighting without weapons is emphasized to underline the disastrous approach of violence and humanity.¹ He is showing the certain violence and conflict depicted in the ancient time as well as what is happening around him nowadays. However, this is the language of an individual artist with his instinctive taste and sense in 20th century. The work is as huge as the Roman sculpture to record the history. The sense of expressiveness and drama is implemented in both huge Pergamon sculpture and Golub’s painting. The concept of narration is parallel to define violence. The authority of a group of people over one another. One dates back to roughly the beginning of Hellinistic Art and era and the other last century. Taking triumphal prospect out to show the brutal side of it to us. Nonetheless, the figures are not recognizable. Neither hero nor actual person to give the generalize the concept of violence and to deny arousing specific attention to a certain person or group. In a sense, he might show the equality among figures to show what exactly they are doing.

⁷ Director of Irish museum of Modern Art.

⁸ Bird, Leon Golub, *Echoes of the Real*, preface.

⁹ Leon Golub, interviewed by Bruce Hooton, 1965

¹ Leon Golub, interviewed by David Procuinar, *The Journal of Contemporary Art*

in his and his wife earlier works the influences of Jean Dubuffet is explicit. Especially, in the disfiguration and deformation of figure of personages. In this period (50s), he had a combinations of figurative art but the abstract taste was highly stronger and intense compared with his later works¹. Visiting works of some masters such as David, Gericault, and Courbet one the one hand, observing the Algerian war one the other hand was overlapping in his intention to paint such scenes in which the concepts of power and violence were prioritized and initiated. All in all, in Europe, he could and had the opportunity to develop his practices more broadly compared with the mainstream that was covered the atmosphere of art and art market.

Last but not least, the enlargement of the surface of his work, particularly the use of acrylic¹ was immensely important and decisive in the production of his works. This was the peak for him to align the content of his work with the materiality and the subject he already chose to work with. The “Gigantomachy”, and “Sphinx” acquired huge size in order to be effective and rhetoric for the visitors. lately, he used this merit and superiority to emphasis on the violation embedded in the following artworks. It surely helped the colors to be dried sooner. Therefore, the sooner they are dried, the more works he could create.

¹ According to Peter Selz¹ (a fellow student of Golub’s at the University of Chicago, a Writing in Art News, 1955

¹ Shira, Wolfe, Agents of Change: Acrylic Paint, ARTLAND MAGAZINE

Details from Pergamon Altar

Gigantomachy II, 1966, Acrylic on linen, 303.5*758.2 CM

Coming back to US

Then coming back to America. The time was a time of intellectual revolution and change in American politics. They settled in New York in 1964. This time, Golub as a political activist who can produce political and social artwork was the central attention. One of the integral point

¹ From left to right, figures:³Alkyoneos, Athena, Ge, and Nike, Pergamon Altar

¹ From left to right, figures⁴ associated with water: Nereus and Doris, Oceanos, and part of Tethys(?). North side of grand staircase, Pergamon Altar (photo:Carole Raddato, CC BY-SA 2.0)

in changing his visual vocabulary and subject and turn them into real worlds was the concept of war, especially in 20th century.¹ Algerian war when he resided in France and Vietnam war when it was going on in the period when he moved to US. One of the effective event in Golub's career was his attendance in a group called "Monster Roster" and "The Artists and Writers Protest" in mid 60s, one with the tendencies of having figurative approach and the other with anti-war and post-war position as artists and writers.¹ Moreover, the pictorial sources of his work was the use of pictures from wars and mass-magazine. "He is a history painter".¹ 7

After passing his earlier works he became more radical to present his works and selecting the subject and even the composition. Hence, dealing with war issues and participating in radicalistic and activist groups and exhibitions were a potential springboard to the theme of his works in his upcoming years.

According to Jon Bird, Golub saw the need to represent critical and ethical commitment with the use of painting and depiction. Recording not by camera but even using camera pictures with artist's intention to underscore what should be seen and shown by viewers in those decades.

It was in early 80s that extensive attention was aroused towards Golub's works by millionaires, dealers, curators and art market describing works as "neo-expressionism". This was aligned with the demise Abstract Expressionism which was reigning for decades in market.¹ additionally, 8 other crucial factors too involved in the underlying, political, economical and social aspects for instance.

¹ Leon Golub, interviewed by David Procuinar, The Journal of Contemporary Art

¹ Beth Ann, Handler, "The Art of Activism", Artists and Writers Protest, the Art Workers' Coalition, and the New York Art Strike Protest the Vietnam War, Yale University, May 2001

¹ Spectres of History, Jon Bird, A Symposium on Leon Golub Royal College of Art Battersea, 1st May 2015

¹ CARRIE RICKEY, I. Slouching Towards Thebes, <https://www.carrierickey.com/articles/try-burning-this-one-asshole/>

Terms in his works

In his works, one is confronted with images of aggressiveness, Power, violence. Mostly in his works we see people in the situation of being suffered from something. But the torments are done by someone else. Thus, the first term in his work is violence. The second term in his work is unlimited power. There are no happy-ending in his works.

The stability and consciousness of the artist is obviously visible in his works in spite of working on over fifty years in this field and subject. Since it is tempting for any artist to recopy one style and well-known collection, he was in stability and aware of changing the subject or even the composition¹ .

9

In every collection in which we have two opposite situations, he is not reflecting the political conflict. In the series called “Assassins”, “Interrogation”, “Napalm”, his tendencies to depict and reinforce the darker side of politics, not showing what the mass is indicating every day to people to consume can be perceived. However, he is challenging the viewers² . Thereby, the characters⁰ who are in an inappropriate situation implicating visitors by showing the reality that was made by political and social decisions in the places where they live. They are being suffered and tortured in silence and loneliness that even the visitors cannot do and enhance the moment. In a sense, canvases painted by Golub is reminding people a sort of documentation as well as photographs. A documentary that is based on the things in which seen and heard by the survivors like the painting titled “The Raft of the Medusa” by Theodore Gericault, narrating the violation, exploitation and aggressiveness.

¹ Portrait collection. In this collection, he kept the same style. However, he had a radical shift in the composition of his work compare with the past.

² Bird, Leon Golub, *Echöes of the Real*, introduction

Théodore Géricault, The Raft of the Medusa, 1818-1819, 491.5 × 716.5 cm, Oil on canvas,
Louvre Museum

These contradiction terms are not only in his work in case of compositions and personages but also in the relation between work of art (canvases) and spectators. moreover, the tensions too between the pattern and materials are applied. This is why his work has become enormously strong and flawless. In a sense, he managed every single element and aspect of his work to eliminate any criticism toward works. Consequently, we are confronted with a work of art like old masters did in the past without inserting any comment for the color harmony, composition, element for the technical term.

in his work, one is not facing with figurative works. It is a figuration and abstraction at the same time. It is because of the accidental time with abstract expressionism. In addition, Golub's understanding of this expressionism dominant and the use of this feature in his work to emphasis and underscore the tension in the field of power and stark condition was absolutely unique. his figurative approach with the combination of expressionism and produce paintings with social tradition that actually engages with spectators.

² <https://www.artsy.net/artwork/theodore-gericault-the-raft-of-the-medusa>

The role of photography is crucial and significant in his work. In those paintings where those personages who have power and are in the positions of power, they are looking out of painting and at visitors. In other words, they are looking at us. This feature is what is functioning in photographs. To consider similar point, he may have wanted to those who are in front of his work imagine and take the place of photograph. Taking a record or witnesses what is happening in order to show it to others who are not believing your experiences.

he considers his work in huge and gigantic sizes. He might have been influenced by the exact size in which abstract expressionism such as Jackson Pollock did and the impression he received from those sizes. Therefore, capturing specific moment like the function of camera in documentation and representing it in huge size like a banner seems to be a protest or a poster in huge size in the hands of people marching for something or showing to those who are against that perception.

Another term in Golub's work is the place of viewers. At first I need to give a contradiction example. In Medieval time and when the depiction of Jesus Christ was with sorrow and grief. Especially, in scenes such as crucifixion those are in front of depiction are highly likely to be responsible for the fate and the moment of the painting². Nowadays, the spectators must have grasped the opposite impressions. Those under torments are unknown on the one hand. On the other hand, they are ordinary and mirror of today's people in the world. They are neither suffering for better life after the death nor dying for their faith. As a result, Golub is trying to show two shocking points at the same time. Firstly, a contradiction interpretation of a situation

² This interpretation made by John Roberts, A Symposium on Leon Golub Royal College of Art Battersea

where people are dying under power of other people. Also, the taste of death in his works are earthly. Secondly, the radical change between the way viewers receive sensible and tangible experiences from the reality that existed in 20th century.

Gigantomachy V, 1965-68

he looked back to contradiction of tragic hero (human muscularity) and machination of power² .

It was a new phase in his work. His wide use of photographs is also visible in this series. They are in awkward situation having physical violence and pain. The personages in this scene are in vulnerable condition, being similar in feature and character. There is not prominent figure as hero and also the result and reason of fight, having obvious violation and aggression as curator Kelly Baum said.²

4

he was depicting the violence to the world. No mention of time and place. He eliminates every simple object that could interference the entire meaning of painting to another level.

Furthermore, ignoring to put additional element in the work.

² Spectres of History, Jon Bird, A Symposium on Leon Golub Royal College of Art Battersea

² LEON GOLUB, Nadja Sa'ei, 'He wanted to get a rise out of people'- the violent paintings of Leon Golub, THE GUARDIAN, 2018

Gigantomachy V, Acrylic on linen, 292*517 cm, Museo Reina Sofia Foundation/USA, 1968

This could be you

the worldwide perspective towards violence is shown in this work. He is also not pointing out to specific violence. He taught that the violence is common in everywhere. he hinted those in power and even other people to put themselves in the situation of personages to know not about the consequences but the common reality in all over around the world. He is mentioning that war does not concern about specific zone and area. He uses harsh expressive manner to depict the black people not for the white one.

Leon Golub, This Could Be You, 2002, Acrylic on linen, 26.25 x 22.5 inches

Vietnam II

it is written in one article that Golub's approach towards creating works as radical painter and

² FIGHTING MEN: GOLUB, VOULKOS, KIRBY, Daniel Duford, FIGHTING MEN: GOLUB, VOULKOS, KIRBY Daniel Duford, Lewis & Clark College, Portland, page 36

activism embarked with his series named Vietnamese with terrifying paintings in 1970.² In this collection we confront with another types of violation. The aggressiveness that hurt human body and make wounds. This time he took more steps and went further in the concept and term of violent by showing cut and wounds on the bodies. Here, he might have reinforced the tendencies of hurting people who are victims. They are victims of the ideology of war that is exerted by a group of people who run the politics. In the relevant group exhibition called “Artists and Writers Protest Against the War in Vietnam” with the anti-war theme, Golub and others argued their opposition with their works of art.² his work ran the idea of violation and destruction that was in war discourse. It is a quote in Guardian Magazine in which describes Golub’s position: “As an activism, his paintings represent the violence he was opposed to”, said Baum.²

8

This was made for public space, due to the fact that the size of work is extensively huge. There are new features in this scene where he used holes by cutting the attached canvases and cinematic composition. It is as if one is witnessing a documentary and the cornerstone part of it frozen for us to observe more. Long horizontal composition remains of panoramic painting and photography to give the immersion of recording the entire event. In addition, cutting canvas was a way to show the awkwardness and to bring viewers to it. Therefore, this work and others in which titled “Vietnam” try to show more the sense of destruction and what is brutally prevalent in war with the use of visual artistic view that the artist had gained during his career.

² Nadja Sayej, “He wanted to get a rise out of people’ – the violent paintings of Leon Golub”, The Guardian, 2018

² Various Artists, “Artists and Writers Protest against the War in Vietnam”, MOMA, 1967, <https://www.moma.org/collection/works/32582>

² Nadja Sayej, “He wanted to get a rise out of people’ – the violent paintings of Leon Golub”, The Guardian, 2018, <https://www.theguardian.com/artanddesign/2018/feb/06/leon-golub-art-new-york-raw-nerve>

Interrogation

Interrogation III, acrylic on canvas, (304.8 x 429.26 cm), 1981

it is written in one article that Golub's approach towards creating works as radical painter and activism embarked with his series named Vietnamese with terrifying paintings in 1970. In this series, he dealt with some discourses. What he depicts was a kind human condition that tend to be hidden in view and are not shown as an individual painting and image on the wall. Among them, the sexual exploitation is more sensible. Also, what he depicts was human condition. One of factor of this series work is the emotional and rhetorical aspects. The extensive use of dark colors and muddy white has doubled the expressiveness paintings even far more than other series. since as a painter who studied history as well as visiting ancient art and monuments, he was so conscious of pose and gestures. Here, Golub is making the visitor guilty to observe his

works for a while and be irresponsible about what they are looking at. He somewhat kicks those unconsciously observing inhumanity.² Moreover, he studied and observe the real and stark pictures of torments. Although he did not just copy the exact and certain picture as they were in the pictures, he changed the situations and gestures of personage so as to imply as much emotions as he can in his works. Moreover, his tendencies to make antiheroic public art can be felt.³ In this work he tried to depict what can be seen on the streets in some countries to us. He is among few artists who can share this type deliberation in their work even if they encounter the dissatisfaction of museums and galleries. as he declared “if you're lucky, end up in a museum”.³ He wants the visitors to see his work as a poster on the walls of every street as public art.³ In addition, the enormous sizes of this series according to him justify his intention to lead his approach to dramatic public art. The intended use of huge size of canvas can sink the visitors to itself as everyday gigantic advertisement as banner and posters in highway and streets to arouse people’s attention and interests.

to confront with this painting and others with the same theme, men and women as visitors may have divergent and parallel impression. At the first sight, the brutality of scene probably grasps the attention and the sense of morality of both gender. Lately, men consider themselves as if they were the assassins and women imagining themselves being under the tortures. To some extent, it is partially apparent, since Golub characterized figures with typical features that can be corresponded to a broad numbers of nationalities with white skin. Here, too he is criticizing

² LEON GOLUB, JEANNE⁹SILVERTHORNE, ARTFORUM

³ Leon Golub, interviewed by David Procuinar, if you're lucky, end up in a museum”.

³ Leon Golub, interviewed by David Procuinar, if you're lucky, end up in a museum”.

³ “I’m sort of interested now² in what I would call a kind of public art which relates to an earlier interest I had in what I might call a ritualistic art.”, Leon Golub, interviewed by Bruce Hooton, 1965

individuals in the act of interrogators in 20th century. Again, mentioning violation does not concern with time and century. It is even if people are dressed stylish and in modern societies.

Quote

Works from left to right: *Combat II* by Leon Golub, color screenprint. National Gallery of Victoria, Melbourne, 1971. Center: *Judith Beheading Holofernes* by Caravaggio, Oil in canvas, 145 x 195 cm, Palazzo Barberini, Rome, 1599. Right: *Judith Beheading Holofernes* by Artemisia Gentileschi, Oil on canvas, 159 x 126 cm, Capodimonte Museum, Naples 1611-12

One may see the similarities in Caravaggio and Gentileschi work depicting Judith. What is important in two artworks is the important element of Baroque style. The action has just been started. But has not finished yet. Mid-time. So the next moment is touchable for us. It has been a long time that referring to history and Baroque was totally forgotten.

The alignment of his perception with the opinion of theoreticians

In this part, it is worth mentioning the definition of a punishment based on what Michel Foucault stated in his book.³ He gave the key points of a shift in public punishment in European country and abolishing the previous gloomy methods that was in public places to more private places. The transition of violation embedded in punishment to become a way of control aiming at regulating individual behavior. Therefore, by the establishments of the prison, authorities have more systematic control over individuals' lives.

What can be discerned from Golub's works may aligned with what Foucault stated about the normalization of punishment and aggressiveness in the society and the other smaller parts. However, there is also an alteration between them. The violation is still exerting by a group of people regardless of being sovereign aggression. Therefore, this kind of discipline might have been chaotic and brutal. Since there are some series in his works regarding tortures, he directly underscoring the aggression in prison and specifically those are in wars and have the authority. It might too mean sovereign power in 18th century by the example made by Foucault or by Golub narrating his time in painting by using photographic evidences.

In other case, the power that Freud describes it to us. The power that exalts and celebrates a thought to cover on the desire of destroy. Freud talked about war: The instinct to destroy is in human beings. Especially those in war and war situations. Instinct of invasion and destruction is in human beings.

The letters exchanged between Albert Einstein and Sigmund Freud reflect their discussions on various topics, primarily centered around the relationship between war, aggression, and human

³ DISCIPLINE AND PUNISH, The Birth of the Prison, Michel Foucault, Translated from the French by Alan Sheridan, place of publication, Penguin Books, 1978

nature.³ He was wondering why⁴the wars between nations are held. Also, he questioned the ambition of every single person who involved in war unintentionally and purposely. Question like, what enthusiasm run people's mind to sacrifice even their own lives? In the series of letters sending to Einstein, Freud described to him the initial ideology of war is like a cover to justify the instinct of destroy and invasion. He too noted that the violence in animal kingdom is akin to the terms in human being. Einstein was too convinced that all leader regardless of being in small and huge groups have the same ideals. Adding that they are not morally considered as leader. In the context of aggression, Freud's psychoanalytic theories suggested that aggressive tendencies were inherent in human nature and could be linked to primal instincts. Thereby, the extensive use of personal force and the brutal struggle of a leader and ruler to extend their rights bring about a situation utilizing instrument of violence to ensure the safety a group of people as citizens, and fellows. He believed that the right is dependent on brute force and violence to retain it. In addition, these aforementioned aspects are linked to erotic and hate, two fundamental human instincts that are parallel to one another. Therefore, the context of love and hate are volatile in terms of power and it becomes much crude in broader scale in a group of people and their relation with a leader and ruler.

notably, having this in mind that, in addition in what we see in Golub's works he may elaborate the content described in Freud's letter with a question: "why". This can be perceived in some of his works apart from other terms embedded in his works.

³ The Einstein-Freud Correspondence (1931-1932), Arizona State University

Golub tried to refuse and break all formulaic factors that was common in market. His work did not have any frame to be against in capitalism structure in art. However, Jacques Derrida's idea about frame and framework of painting and a work of art are rooted in philosophical concepts. One of his insights regarding the frame that frame is not neutral and transparent structure. Nevertheless, integral part. In the essay "The Truth in Painting", says that a frame is not a simple border that separates artwork from its surrounding. Rather, it is a meaningful quality.³ he underscores the significance in interpretation and presentation of artwork. Also, how a frame can be compatible or incompatible with a work of art.

Historical and evidential terms influences

Violence, after the Vietnam war, in 70s, when Richard Nixon was forced to finish the war, the term of violence became more prevalent in many artists' artworks. One has to ask themselves why the theme of his work is the Vietnam War? America was the first to finish the war. America was the one to insist on bringing people to the court. But at the same time, America was one of the main reason that we can see that Vietnam was flooded buy blood. At the end of 60s we have the punishment of Israel. Also, the so called Sabra and Shatila massacre. These were happening in the time Leon Golub was living and observing.

As a radical opposed stereotypical

He tried to refuse all formulaic factors that was common in market. The contradiction in the

³ DERRIDA, JACQUES, THE TRUTH IN PAINTING, Translated by Geoff Bennington and Ian McLeon, The University of Chicago Press, Chicago and London, 1987

deliberation of Modernism art is highly felt in his works. His work did not have any frame to be against in capitalism structure in art. He was against the theory of Adorno. In the Adorno Theory he was Deconstructivism artist. Regarding to titles of his works in which were chosen subtly and simply pointing out the direct to his representation with actual events, Mao's quotation that said "Power comes from the barrel of a gun"³ can attributed as a title for every work of Golub, since his opposition with the ideologies of war in Mao, Marxist, American imperialism in central America and Africa, and any brutal principle that engage and admire violation is fitted and suitable.

Conclusion

To sum up, Leon Golub as an American artist working in Europe and America has been influenced by key artists in art history and even ancient art. He closely observed at the sequences and merit of art works and struggle to superimpose the features in the artworks that had been done before him and integrate those elements with his day's content. In a sense, he combined the issue of violation which had been rooted in ancient art with his time issues not only to have a copy and the same content in 20th century but also he created postwar version of that content as other artists did such as Pablo Picasso. His perspective toward the term of aggressiveness also aligned with what some philosophers argued in his time. Thus, there are canvases with an extensive underlying concept from the artist that visually based on history and the representation

³ H. Druzin, Bryan, Li, Jéssica, The Power of the Keystroke: Is Social Media the Radical Democratizing Force We've Been Led to Believe it is?, published by Harvard Human Rights Journal February 2015, 1

of violation in art history in general. The common term that is neither undeniable in the past nor in the today's world.

Bibliography

1. SMART MUSEUM OF ART, THE UNIVERSITY OF CHICAGO, THE ROSTER: LEON GOLUB, <https://smartmuseum.uchicago.edu/blog/the-roster-leon-golub/>
2. Leo Golub, *Echoes of the real*, Jon Bird, published by Reaktion Books, 2000
3. AT THE MET WITH: Leon Golub and Nancy Spero; 2 Artists Always Prowling For Ideas To Use Again, New York Times, By Michael Kimmelman, Jan. 5, 1996
4. Leon Golub, interviewed by David Procutiar, JOURNAL OF CONTEMPORARY ART
5. Leon Golub, interviewed by Bruce Hooton,, Oral history interview with Leon Golub, Archives of American Art, Smithsonian Institution, 1965
6. Spectres of History, Jon Bird, A Symposium on Leon Golub Royal College of Art Battersea, 1st May 2015
7. Empathy and Negation: Leon Golub's Realism, John Roberts, A Symposium on Leon Golub Royal College of Art Battersea, 1st May 2015
8. LEON GOLUB, JEANNE SILVERTHORNE, ARTFORUM
9. LEON GOLUB, Nadja Sayei, 'He wanted to get a rise out of people'-the violent paintings of Leon Golub, THE GUARDIAN, 2018,
<https://www.theguardian.com/artanddesign/2018/feb/06/leon-golub-art-new-york-raw-nerve>

10. Raddato, Carole, Pergamon Altar, CC BY-SA 2.0, <https://smarthistory.org/the-pergamon-altar/>
11. Shira, Wolfe, Agents of Change: Acrylic Paint, ARTLAND MAGAZINE.
<https://magazine.artland.com/agents-of-change-acrylic-paint/>
12. Various Artists with Rudolf Baranik, Paul Burlin, Charles Cajori, William Copley, Allan D'Arcangelo, Mark di Suvero, Leon Golub, Charles Hinman, Louise Nevelson, Irving Petlin, Ad Reinhardt, Jack Sonenberg, George Sugarman, Carol Summers, David Weinrib, Adja Yunkers, "Artists and Writers Protest against the War in Vietnam", MOMA, 1967,
<https://www.moma.org/collection/works/32582>
13. Nadja Sayej, "He wanted to get a rise out of people" – the violent paintings of Leon Golub", The Guardian, 2018, <https://www.theguardian.com/artanddesign/2018/feb/06/leon-golub-art-new-york-raw-nerve>
14. CARRIE RICKEY, I. Slouching Towards Thebes, <https://www.carrierickey.com/articles/try-burning-this-one-asshole/>
15. H. Druzin, Bryan, Li, Jessica, The Power of the Keystroke: Is Social Media the Radical Democratizing Force We've Been Led to Believe it is?, published by Harvard Human Rights Journal February 2015, 1
16. Théodore Géricault, The Raft of the Medusa, <https://www.artsy.net/artwork/theodore-gericault-the-raft-of-the-medusa>
17. DERRIDA, JACQUES, THE TRUTH IN PAINTING, Translated by Geoff Bennington and Ian McLeón, The University of Chicago Press, Chicago and London, 1987

18. The Einstein-Freud Correspondence (1931-1932), Arizona State University
19. Beth Ann, Handler, "The Art of Activism", Artists and Writers Protest, the Art Workers' Coalition, and the New York Art Strike Protest the Vietnam War, Yale University, May 2001
20. DISCIPLINE AND PUNISH, The Birth of the Prison, Michel Foucault, Translated from the French by Alan Sheridan, place of publication, Penguin Books, 1978
21. FIGHTING MEN: GOLUB, VOULKOS, KIRBY, Daniel Duford, FIGHTING MEN: GOLUB, VOULKOS, KIRBY Daniel Duford, Lewis & Clark College, Portland, page 36
22. Golub, Leon, Combat II, 1971, <https://www.ngv.vic.gov.au/explore/collection/work/24748/>
23. Caravaggio, Judith Beheading Holofernes, 1599, <https://barberinicorsini.org/en/opera/judith-beheading-holofernes/>
24. Gentileschi, Artemisia, Judith Beheading Holofernes, 1611-12, <https://www.khanacademy.org/humanities/renaissance-reformation/baroque-art1/baroque-italy/a/gentileschi-judith-slaying-holofernes>